

Chemical Examination of *Evodia fraxinifolia* Hook

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Evodia fraxinifolia (Rutaceae) is widely distributed in the subtropical Himalayas from Sikkim to Nepal. The plant is reported to be useful as an antipyretic in Indo-China¹. Recently Talapatra *et al.*² reported the isolation of isobauerenol^{3,4} from the stem bark of the plant. We therefore wish to record our independent investigation on the same plant and isolation of limonin⁵ and β -sitosterol besides isobauerenol.

Dried and powdered bark (2 Kg.) of *E. fraxinifolia*, was extracted with benzene in a soxhlet apparatus for 8 hrs. The gummy residue (23 g.) left after solvent evaporation was separated into ether soluble and ether insoluble fractions.

The ether soluble fraction (17 g.) was directly chromatographed over activated alumina (250 g.). Elution with a mixture of benzene and ether (4 : 1) yielded a gummy solid (2 g.) which on rechromatography and crystallisation from methanol gave an alcohol (0.22 g.), C₃₀H₅₀O, m.p. 166–169°, (α)_D+46.1° (CHCl₃). Acetylation of the alcohol (0.2 g.) gave an acetate (0.07 g.), m.p. 211–214°, (α)_D+44° (CHCl₃), which was identified (mixed m.p.) as isobauerenyl acetate^{3,4}. Jones' oxidation⁶ of isobauerenol (0.32 g.) furnished isobauerenone³ (0.17 g.), m.p. 173–176°, (α)_D+70.8° (CHCl₃), that showed a positive Cotton effect in O.R.D. curve. Isobauerenone (0.17 g.) was reduced by the Huang-Minlon procedure to isobauerenol (0.09 g.), m.p. 150–154°, (α)_D+45.9° (CHCl₃).

Further elution of the column with a mixture of benzene and ether (1 : 4) gave a gummy solid (0.4 g.) which on crystallisation from methanol yielded a solid (0.11 g.), m.p. 136–138°, identified as β -sitosterol.

The ether insoluble portion (6 g.) was chromatographed over a column of silica gel (60 g.). Elution with chloroform gave a gummy solid (2.8 g.), that on repeated crystallisations from methanol furnished a solid (0.6 g.), C₂₆H₃₀O₈, m.p. 293–295°, (α)_D–131.6°, M⁺ 470.

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(Found : C, 66.48; H, 6.57. Calculated for : $C_{26}H_{30}O_8$: C, 66.37; H, 6.43%). The I.R. spectra showed peaks at 1765 cm^{-1} (γ -lactone), 1710 cm^{-1} (six-membered ring saturated ketone) and 1515 and 875 cm^{-1} (β -substituted furan). The compound was identified⁷ (mixed m.p. and I.R.) with limonin⁵.

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